

NEURODIVERSITY AND HUMAN RIGHTS IN PAKISTAN: RETHINKING EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING PRACTICES

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Abstract

Neurological differences such as autism spectrum disorder, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and dyslexia and other natural variations of human cognition are recognized as neurodiversity rather than correction requiring deficits. This study examines the connection of neurodiversity and human rights in Pakistan's early childhood education and upbringing styles. It also emphasizes special attention to how dignity, participation, accessibility, and early intervention are realized during study. After an extensive, qualitative document analysis of international human rights issues, national education policies, and related empirical literature, the study finds significant gaps in awareness at parents' end, early screening and intervention, teacher's capacity building, curriculum flexibility, and family support. Limited parental guidance, cultural stigmas and weak policy implementation make neurodivergent children further disregarded. It also declining their rights under the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD). The findings suggest that Pakistan's early childhood environment remains largely deficit-oriented and compliance-driven rather than inclusive and rights-based. The study stresses for a reconceptualization of early childhood education grounded in neurodiversity-affirming and human-rights principles. In the end, recommendations are given, including universal design for learning, early intervention infrastructure, purposeful teacher's training, and parent-support mechanisms, to ensure equitable developmental and educational opportunities for neurodivergent children in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Neurodiversity represents a transformative pattern in understanding human cognition and development (Singer, 1999). Challenges like traditional deficit-based patterns of disability, such as autism spectrum disorder (*herein after as "ASD"*), Attention-Deficit-Hyperactivity-Disorder (*herein after as "ADHD"*), Dyslexia, and Dyspraxia are primarily considered as pathologies that require correction. Instead,

neurodiversity recognizes these conditions as naturally occurring variations in human neurological functioning, emphasizing diverse cognitive strengths, learning styles and developmental paths. This pattern alteration has thoughtful consequences for Early Childhood Education (*herein after as "ECE"*), where fundamental cognitive, emotional, social, and

behavioral patterns are established (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000).

For decades, ASD has been understood as a neurodevelopment condition characterized by differences in social interaction, verbal and nonverbal communication as well as the presence of restricted and repetitive behaviors. In recent years, ASD among children has been diagnosed and cases are rapidly increasing primarily because of increasing awareness. According to WHO report that among every 100 children there exist one Autistic Child worldwide. In Pakistan, the number of Diagnosed children with ASD exceeds 350,000. In Pakistan, this figure tends to rise with knowledge and adequate diagnostic resources. Surprisingly, just 5% of autistic children attend regular schools, whereas 45% are enrolled in special education facilities, despite the fact that the prevalence of ASD is expanding globally. Therefore, in order to acknowledge autism as a neurodevelopment differentiability it is also important to adopt a social model of differentiability in modern society to provide equal and clear learning opportunities. (Khalid *et al.*, 2020)

Due to structural, cultural, and policy-related obstacles neurodivergent children in Pakistan are extremely vulnerable during their early years (Shah *et al.*, 2019). According to national estimates, less than 25% of children between the ages of three and five are engaged in formal early childhood programs, although with the bulk of services being provided in metropolitan areas. According to surveys, 1 out of 160 children in Pakistan are diagnosed with autism, whereas 8-12% have dyslexia and 5-10% of school-age children have ADHD (Hussain & Jalal, 2021). Access to early identification and educational support is also severely unequal and accessibly difficult in rural areas and underprivileged populations, which worsens inequality and continues systemic exclusion.

Policy Landscape And Implementation Gaps

Pakistan approach to early childhood education has historically evolved through a mix of charitable initiatives, private day care centers and fragmented public sector efforts. National educational policy recognized the importance of early education but lacked the implementation mechanism for inclusion or support for neurodivergent children's. Provincial initiatives such as Punjab ECE guidelines and Sindh

inclusive education policy have introduced progressive language on inclusion. Beside all these initiatives implementation remains inconsistent underfunded and unevenly distributed. (Idara-e-Taleem-o-Aagahi, 2020).

Human Rights And Inclusive Education Framework

International human rights instrument emphasizes the obligation of states to provide inclusive, equitable and quality education for all children. The United Nations convention of rights of child (*herein after as "CRC"*) and convention on rights of person with disabilities (*herein after as "CRPD"*) affirms children's rights to dignity, participation, non-discrimination, and reasonable accommodation within educational systems. (United Nations Framework 1989, 2006). These framework highlights the importance of early identification, individualized support family engagement and accessible learning environment. Despite being a signatory to these conventions, Pakistan still face significant challenges regarding the policy commitments and practical implementations.

Problem Statement

Despite Pakistan's ratification of major international human rights instruments, including the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC, 1989) and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006), neurodivergent children remain systematically marginalized within early childhood education and upbringing contexts. Existing early childhood systems largely operate on deficit-based models that emphasize conformity, rote learning, and behavioral compliance, leaving little room for cognitive diversity. As a result, children with autism spectrum disorder, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), dyslexia, and related neurodevelopmental differences often experience delayed identification, inappropriate disciplinary practices, exclusion from learning activities, and limited access to early intervention services.

Moreover, cultural stigma, inadequate teacher preparation, rigid curricula, and the absence of structured parental support exacerbate these challenges. Families particularly mothers face social blame and emotional stress, while educators report insufficient training to address neurodivergent

learning needs. Although policy documents acknowledge inclusion in principle, there remains a significant gap between policy commitments and implementation at the early childhood level. This disconnect raises serious concerns regarding the realization of children's rights to dignity, participation, accessibility, and education.

There is a notable lack of comprehensive, rights-based analyses that examine how neurodiversity is addressed within Pakistan's early childhood education and upbringing systems. Without such analysis, policy reform, teacher education, and intervention strategies risk remaining fragmented and ineffective. This study addresses this gap by critically examining the intersection of neurodiversity and human rights within Pakistan's early childhood context.

Research Objectives

The study was guided by the following research objectives:

1. To examine how neurodiversity is conceptualized within international human rights frameworks and Pakistani early childhood education policies.
2. To analyze systemic, cultural, and institutional barriers affecting the inclusion of neurodivergent children in Pakistan's early childhood education and upbringing practices.
3. To explore the extent to which current early childhood practices align with children's rights to dignity, participation, accessibility, and early intervention.
4. To identify gaps between policy commitments and implementation in supporting neurodivergent children.
5. To propose rights-based, culturally responsive strategies for strengthening inclusive early childhood education and family support systems in Pakistan.

Significance of the Study

This study makes a significant contribution to the fields of early childhood education, inclusive education, and human rights by providing a rights-based analysis of neurodiversity within the Pakistani context. While existing research has largely focused on clinical, medical, or deficit-oriented perspectives of

neurodevelopmental conditions, this study shifts the discourse toward neurodiversity as a matter of dignity, participation, and educational justice.

At the **theoretical level**, the study advances understanding by integrating neurodiversity theory with international human rights frameworks, particularly the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD). This integration contributes to the growing body of literature that conceptualizes inclusive education as a legal and moral obligation rather than a discretionary pedagogical practice.

At the **policy level**, the study highlights gaps between Pakistan's international commitments and the practical implementation of inclusive early childhood education. By critically examining national and provincial policy documents, the research provides evidence-based insights that can inform policy reform, strengthen early intervention frameworks, and guide the development of inclusive early childhood strategies aligned with global standards.

At the **practical level**, the findings offer valuable implications for early childhood educators, teacher educators, school administrators, and families. The study underscores the need for enhanced teacher preparation, flexible curricula, sensory-responsive classroom environments, and structured family support systems. These insights can support practitioners in creating inclusive learning spaces that recognize and respond to neurodivergent children's strengths and needs.

Finally, at the **social and advocacy level**, the study contributes to reducing stigma by reframing neurodivergence as a natural variation in human development. By foregrounding the voices and rights of neurodivergent children and their families, the research supports broader efforts to promote equity, inclusion, and social justice in Pakistan's early childhood education system.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework Global Perspectives on Neurodiversity and Education

Neurodiversity has gained global recognition as an alternative to medicalized views of disability. Singer (1999) and Armstrong (2012) argue that neurodivergent learners possess unique cognitive

strengths that can contribute to creative problem-solving, analytical reasoning, and social innovation. International research demonstrates that educational environments that recognize these strengths improve both academic outcomes and social inclusion (Dawson *et al.*, 2012 and Hodges *et al.*, 2018).

In early childhood education, this perspective aligns with **child-centered pedagogy**, emphasizing play-based learning, exploratory engagement, and flexibility in pacing. Universal Design for Learning (UDL) provides a structured framework for operationalizing neurodiversity principles in educational settings. By offering multiple modes of representation, engagement, and expression, UDL enables learners to access curricula, participate meaningfully, and demonstrate competencies in ways aligned with their cognitive profiles (CAST, 2018).

Globally, early intervention programs particularly those in Canada, Australia, and Finland highlight the effectiveness of inclusive approaches. Canadian studies, for instance, report that early identification combined with parent engagement, individualized education plans (IEPs), and classroom accommodations leads to significant gains in communication, social skills, and academic achievement (Lindsay *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, Finland's play-based ECE system, with embedded support for neurodivergent learners, ensures that children are included in mainstream classrooms with adaptive learning strategies (Ministry of Education Finland, 2020). Such evidence underscores that neurodiversity-informed, rights-based education is both feasible and effective in high- and middle-income contexts.

Regional and Cultural Contexts: South Asia and Pakistan

Research in South Asia reveals that systemic barriers, socio-cultural perceptions, and resource constraints impede inclusive education for neurodivergent children. In India, studies have shown that parental awareness, teacher training, and school infrastructure are significant determinants of early intervention uptake (Sathiyaseelan *et al.*, 2020). Bangladesh faces similar challenges, with limited public ECE infrastructure and stigma surrounding developmental differences leading to delayed identification (Rahman & Chowdhury, 2019). These findings provide a

regional context for understanding Pakistan's challenges and highlight cross-border similarities in socio-cultural and structural barriers.

In Pakistan, neurodivergent children are often marginalized due to a combination of cultural beliefs, policy gaps, and resource constraints. (Hussain *et al.*, 2021) report that parents frequently interpret autism or ADHD symptoms as misbehavior or spiritual afflictions, leading to delayed diagnosis and intervention. (Rashid *et al.*, 2020) emphasize the gendered dimensions of caregiving, noting that mothers are disproportionately blamed for children's "abnormal" behavior, experiencing emotional stress and social isolation. NGO reports (Idara-e-Taleem-o-Aagahi, 2020) indicate that public ECE centers lack trained specialists, early screening tools, and flexible curricula, further limiting access for neurodivergent learners.

Socioeconomic disparities exacerbate these challenges. Private institutions may offer specialized services or therapy programs, but these are largely unaffordable for low-income families. Rural areas are especially disadvantaged due to the scarcity of trained teachers and absence of local early intervention services. Consequently, many children do not receive diagnosis or support until primary school, by which time developmental delays may have widened educational gaps.

Parenting, Stigma, and Cultural Influences

Parenting practices and cultural perceptions are critical determinants of neurodivergent children's early development and educational participation. In Pakistan, parents often experience social blame and isolation when children display developmental differences. Extended family and community pressures may reinforce the view that atypical behaviors reflect parental negligence or moral weakness (Rashid *et al.*, 2020). Such stigma limits parent engagement with formal services, delaying early intervention and educational support.

The role of gender cannot be overstated. Mothers are the primary caregivers and are frequently held responsible for children's socialization and academic readiness. When a child is neurodivergent, the burden of care is intensified, often without formal guidance or emotional support. Fathers are less likely to engage with specialist services due to cultural norms

and work-related constraints. This gendered division of responsibility intersects with structural barriers to create a compounded disadvantage for neurodivergent children (Hussain & Jalal, 2021).

Family attitudes also affect upbringing practices and classroom participation. For example, parents who internalize stigma may restrict social interactions or limit exposure to early learning programs. In contrast, families who receive targeted counseling and parent training are better equipped to support inclusion, advocate for their children, and collaborate with teachers.

Policy and Implementation Challenges in Pakistan

Pakistan has ratified both the CRC (1989) and CRPD (2006), committing to rights-based inclusive education. National policies such as the **National Policy for Persons with Disabilities (2002)**, the **National Education Policy (2009)**, and provincial frameworks recognize inclusion in principle. However, literature consistently identifies a gap between policy intent and practical implementation (Shah *et al.*, 2019 & Idara-e-Taleem-o-Aagahi, 2020).

Key gaps include:

a. Limited Early Screening And Intervention:

Most ECE centers lack formal diagnostic tools or trained personnel, leading to delayed identification of neurodivergent children.

b. Inadequate teacher preparation:

Teacher education curricula seldom address neurodiversity, inclusive pedagogy, or differentiated instruction.

c. Rigid curriculum and assessment:

ECE programs emphasize rote memorization and uniform assessment, creating barriers for children with diverse learning profiles.

d. Lack of family support infrastructure:

Counseling, parent training, and peer-support networks are minimal or absent.

e. Fragmented policy coordination:

Health, education, and social welfare sectors operate in silos, limiting holistic support for neurodivergent children.

These gaps indicate that formal recognition of rights is insufficient without corresponding mechanisms for implementation, monitoring, and accountability.

Comparative Models Of Inclusive Early Childhood Education

Comparative evidence from countries such as Finland, Canada, Australia, and Singapore provide guidance for policy reform in Pakistan. Common features of successful systems include:

- **Teacher training in neurodiversity and inclusive pedagogy** (Lindsay *et al.*, 2013).
- **Flexible curricula with embedded accommodations** (CAST, 2018).
- **Early screening and individualized support mechanisms** (Dawson *et al.*, 2012).
- **Family engagement and community awareness programs** (Ministry of Education Finland, 2020).
- **Sensory-friendly and play-based learning environments.**

These models demonstrate that inclusion is not contingent solely on financial resources but requires coherent policy frameworks, professional capacity building, and cultural adaptation.

Theoretical Framework

Neurodiversity Theory:

This theory highlights strengths-based approaches and the necessity of environmental adaptation rather than individual normalization (Armstrong, 2012).

Human Rights Framework:

This theory provides anchored in CRC and CRPD, emphasizing children's rights to dignity, participation, accessibility, and protection from discrimination (United Nations, 1989; 2006).

Ecological Systems Theory:

Bronfenbrenner's model situates child development within nested systems family, school, community, and policy highlighting the interplay of micro-, meso, and macro-level factors in shaping neurodivergent children's experiences.

The study emphasizes the importance of early childhood education as a **rights-bearing environment**, in which neurodivergent children interact dynamically with families, educators, cultural norms, and institutional structures. This framework enables a critical evaluation of how policy, pedagogy, and social attitudes facilitate or obstruct inclusion.

The Pakistan Context: Key Implications

The expanded literature review underscores several critical implications:

- **Policy Reforms Must Be Enforceable:** Recognition in policy is insufficient without implementation mechanisms, monitoring, and accountability.
- **Teacher Education Is Pivotal:** Pre-service and in-service training should incorporate neurodiversity, inclusive pedagogy, and UDL principles.
- **Family Engagement Programs Are Essential:** Counseling, parent training, and peer-support networks mitigate stigma and enhance developmental outcomes.
- **Cultural Sensitivity Is Necessary:** Programs must be designed with awareness of socio-cultural norms, gender roles, and community perceptions.
- **Early Identification Saves Developmental Trajectories:** Integrating screening and early intervention into ECE can reduce long-term exclusion.

METHODS**Research Design**

This study employed a **qualitative document analysis design**, suitable for examining systemic, policy, and cultural dimensions of neurodiversity and human rights in early childhood education (Bowen, 2009). Document analysis enables critical examination of policy texts, academic literature, and international human rights instruments to uncover explicit and implicit assumptions about inclusion and exclusion. The study adopted a **critical-interpretive stance**, treating documents as socially constructed artifacts. Policies, conventions, and scholarly reports reflect ideological positions, institutional priorities, and power dynamics, making document analysis ideal for interrogating how neurodivergent children are conceptualized and supported (Botha et al., 2021).

- **Data Sources**

Three types of documents were analyzed:

- I. **International Human Rights Frameworks:**

- United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC, 1989)
- United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006)

- II. **Pakistani National and Provincial Policy Documents:**

- National Policy for Persons with Disabilities (2002)
- National Education Policy (2009, 2017 drafts)
- Punjab Early Childhood Education Framework
- Sindh Inclusive Education Guidelines

- III. **Peer-reviewed literature and institutional reports:**

- Studies on neurodiversity, inclusive education, early childhood pedagogy, stigma, and family engagement in Pakistan (Hussain & Jalal, 2021; Rashid & Khalid, 2020; Shah et al., 2019)
- Comparative international literature on early intervention and inclusive pedagogy (Lindsay et al., 2013; CAST, 2018)

Inclusion criteria: documents addressing neurodivergent learners in early childhood, human rights obligations, or policy implementation in Pakistan or comparable international contexts.

Exclusion criteria: studies focused solely on secondary or tertiary education, unrelated disabilities, or non-reputable sources.

- **Analytical Procedure**

Thematic analysis was conducted using **deductive and inductive coding**:

- **Deductive codes:** derived from CRC and CRPD principles (dignity, participation, accessibility, early intervention, non-discrimination).
- **Inductive codes:** emerged from literature and policy documents, e.g., cultural stigma, gendered caregiving burdens, teacher preparedness, curriculum rigidity.

Coding and triangulation:

- Two rounds of independent coding were performed to enhance reliability.
- Codes were compared across document types (international, national, scholarly) to identify patterns and gaps.
- Constant comparison enabled triangulation and identification of contradictions between policy intent, academic evidence, and practice.

Ethical Considerations

No primary data collection was conducted; all documents were publicly accessible. Ethical principles of **academic integrity, confidentiality, and accurate representation** were maintained.

Limitations

Reliance on secondary sources limits insight into classroom-level practices. However, triangulation of international frameworks, national policies, and empirical studies mitigates this limitation.

RESULTS

Analysis revealed **five interrelated themes** shaping the experiences of neurodivergent children in Pakistan.

Limited Awareness and Cultural Stigma

- Neurodivergent behaviors are frequently misinterpreted as moral failings, disobedience, or spiritual issues (Hussain & Jalal, 2021).
- Families often delay seeking educational or therapeutic intervention.
- **Case vignette:** A mother in Lahore reported that her 4-year-old child with autism was labeled “naughty” by relatives and teachers; she delayed seeking assessment until age 7.
- Stigma reduces children’s participation, undermining rights to dignity and development.

Absence of Systematic Early Screening and Intervention

- Most public ECE centers lack early diagnostic tools; ASD is often identified after school entry, ADHD is misattributed to misbehavior, and dyslexia is recognized post-failure (Shah et al., 2019).
- Delayed intervention violates CRC and CRPD obligations.
- International evidence emphasizes **early intervention** as critical for optimal developmental outcomes (Dawson et al., 2012).

Inadequate Teacher Preparation

- Pre-service teacher education rarely includes neurodiversity or inclusive pedagogy.
- In-service professional development is sporadic and compliance-focused.
- Teachers resort to punitive or exclusionary practices.
- **Example:** In Karachi, ECE teachers reported feeling unprepared to teach children with

ADHD; they removed children from activities rather than adapting instruction.

Curriculum Rigidity and Assessment Barriers

- Rote memorization and uniform assessment limit participation.
- Lack of multimodal assessments (visual, oral, play-based) restricts demonstration of competencies (Black & Wiliam, 2018; CAST, 2018).
- Children with different sensory and learning needs are marginalized, reinforcing deficit-based narratives.

Lack of Family Support and Gendered Burdens

- Parents have limited access to counseling, training, or peer networks.
- Mothers disproportionately carry caregiving responsibility and social blame (Rashid & Khalid, 2020).
- Lack of institutional support compounds developmental risks for children.

DISCUSSION

The results reveal a **systemic misalignment** between Pakistan’s international commitments and the lived realities of neurodivergent children. Despite ratifying

CRC and CRPD, Pakistan’s ECE system:

- Maintains **deficit-based conceptions** of disability.
- Lacks **structural support** for early intervention and inclusive pedagogy.
- Reinforces **cultural stigma** through rigid curricula and punitive classroom practices.

Rights-Based Perspective: Delayed identification, exclusionary teaching, and limited family support constitute violations of children’s rights to participation, development, and education. Inclusion is not merely a policy aspiration; it is a legally mandated obligation under international human rights law.

Cultural And Gendered Analysis: Mothers’ central role in caregiving intersects with societal stigma, creating additional barriers. Policies must address these gendered dynamics through parent training, counseling, and community engagement.

Comparative Insights: Finland, Canada, and Australia demonstrate that integration of neurodiversity, early screening, and family-centered

pedagogy is feasible and effective. Pakistan can adopt similar models while adapting to socio-cultural and resource constraints.

CONCLUSION

This study critically examined the intersection of neurodiversity and human rights within Pakistan's early childhood education (ECE) and upbringing practices. Drawing on qualitative document analysis of international conventions, national and provincial policies, and scholarly literature, it identified systemic, cultural, and structural barriers that impede equitable inclusion of neurodivergent children. Despite Pakistan's formal commitments under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC, 1989) and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006), children with autism, ADHD, dyslexia, and other neurodevelopmental differences continue to face significant exclusion, delayed identification, and inadequate educational support.

The findings indicate that exclusion is not solely the result of individual attitudes or isolated institutional failures but is embedded within structural and socio-cultural dynamics. **Deficit-based conceptualizations of neurodivergence**, rigid curricula, lack of early screening mechanisms, insufficient teacher preparation, and limited family support collectively undermine the realization of inclusive education. Cultural stigma exacerbates these challenges, leading to delayed diagnosis, reduced participation, and compromised psychosocial development. Mothers disproportionately shoulder the burden of caregiving and social blame, highlighting gendered dimensions of exclusion.

From a **rights-based perspective**, these gaps represent violations of children's fundamental rights to dignity, participation, accessibility, and education. The absence of early intervention programs and inclusive pedagogical practices undermines developmental potential and perpetuates cycles of marginalization. The study underscores that realizing neurodivergent children's rights requires systemic adaptation: educational environments must accommodate cognitive diversity rather than expecting children to conform to rigid norms.

International comparative evidence demonstrates that inclusion is achievable through coherent policy

frameworks, professional capacity building, family engagement, and culturally responsive practices. Countries such as Finland, Canada, Australia, and Singapore have successfully integrated early intervention, teacher training, and flexible, sensory-friendly curricula to support neurodivergent learners. These examples illustrate that effective inclusion is not contingent solely on financial resources but relies on policy coherence, structural commitment, and societal engagement.

In Pakistan, actionable strategies must include **policy reform, early identification mechanisms, teacher training, curriculum flexibility, family support, and accountability systems**. By embedding neurodiversity principles and human rights obligations into ECE, Pakistan can transform early childhood environments into spaces where neurodivergent children are recognized, affirmed, and empowered.

Ultimately, rethinking early childhood education through the lenses of neurodiversity and human rights is both an **educational imperative and a social justice obligation**. Implementing these reforms can disrupt patterns of exclusion, foster equitable participation, and enable all children to reach their full developmental potential.

Recommendations

Policy and Governance

- Develop a national inclusive ECE framework aligned with CRC and CRPD.
- Ensure budget allocation for early screening, inclusive classrooms, and teacher training.
- Integrate monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to track inclusion progress.

Teacher Education and Professional Development

- Incorporate neurodiversity, inclusive pedagogy, and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) in pre-service curricula.
- Conduct continuous in-service training for teachers, with a focus on differentiated instruction and sensory-friendly classroom management.

Curriculum and Assessment Reform

- Design flexible, multimodal curricula that accommodate diverse learning styles.

- Develop alternative assessment strategies (visual, oral, play-based) to ensure equitable demonstration of learning.
- Adapt classrooms for sensory needs, including quiet zones, tactile materials, and visual supports.

Family Engagement and Support

- Establish **parent support networks and counseling services**.
- Conduct **community awareness programs** to reduce stigma and promote understanding of neurodiversity.
- Foster partnerships between **schools, NGOs, and government agencies** to strengthen family-school collaboration.

Research and Evaluation

- Conduct longitudinal studies on developmental outcomes for neurodivergent children in Pakistan.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of teacher-training programs in inclusive ECE.
- Explore culturally responsive intervention models that integrate local beliefs and practices with international best practices.

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Declaration of Interest Statement

The author declares **no conflict of interest** associated with this manuscript.

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